

**A STUDY OF PROFESSIONALS SATISFACTION TOWARDS GREEN BANKING
INITIATIVES OF IMPORTANT COMMERCIAL BANKS AT PUTTUR DAKSHINA
KANNADA**

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Abstract

Core banking has replaced traditional banking as the preferred mode of operation because it now provides services that can be fully customized. The need to act quickly while taking into account the changing physical environment, the depletion of natural resources, and meeting customer expectations is the biggest task confronting bankers. Climate change, an increase in paper use, and carbon emissions are just a few examples of current patterns. Bankers in Puttur, Dakshina Kannada District, should now urge and inform their clients to use technologically based products and go paperless. The purpose of this research is to comprehend the attitude of professional workers. A non-parametric test is used to assemble and assess the data that was gathered. The study's findings indicate that there is no association between respondents' levels of happiness and their use of green banking services.

Keywords: Core banking, customized, Climate and Confronting, Non-parametric

Introduction:

Current abrupt changes in the physical climate are not healthy for the nation or its citizens. This will make the atmosphere hotter, spread epidemic diseases, and have a long-term detrimental effect on people's health. Research carried out by a leading research firm in the world have clearly stated that the rapid cause for this abrupt climatic change is due to the destruction in our natural resources, tampering our natural ecological systems, increasing fast urbanization by reducing & clearing more than required trees (reducing greenery & increasing pollution), using more air coolers (AC) etc. Human beings will directly experience the effects of this, which will result in a shorter life expectancy, more victims of deadly epidemic diseases, and a danger to our future generations. On the other hand, the Indian government has ordered the businesses to engage in corporate social duty. When it comes to the banks' role, they have a better one to perform. On the one hand, their employees must encourage clients to switch to paperless banking. (Mobile, Internet & POS swiping). The following benefits to consumers are associated with transactions made through paperless banking:

- This will drastically cut down on processing time and related expenses.
- Saves trees by reducing paper usage (Paperless).
- Minimize lingering in line at a bank for a service while you wait for your turn.
- Online and mobile payments.
- Better instruction in technology (Use of Apps).
- Improved transactional speed.

In this instance we discover that this will also assist with lowering client travel time as well as fuel usage. Customers can easily view their transactions and complete them on time and without any paperwork hassles. Banks today are compelled to conduct research periodically to enhance their goods and services and to add all of their goods to their websites. Although green banking goods and services are relatively new to the market, they have advanced significantly in recent years. Customers find it simpler & more practical to complete their transactions while seated in a specific location. The bank's environmentally friendly goods are popular with young people who are very knowledgeable about technology. The following goods and services are currently offered by banks for the benefit of their clients, and they are as follows:

1. Green current and savings accounts.
2. Green financing.
3. Green Lending.
4. Green credit cards.
5. Green Insurance
6. Green NRI accounts and transfers.
7. Green Demat funds and associated products.

The following are the green banking products and services that institutions currently provide to their clients:

1. E-statements
2. Electronic checks
3. cellular finance
4. Banking via phone.
5. Miss phone service
6. Committed relationship coordinators.
7. Calling points for inquiries
8. Toll-free lines are 8.
9. Services for paying bills.
10. Recharges for mobile and DTH (cable)
11. Transfers of money
12. RTGS (Real time gross settlements)

The banks immediately provide the aforementioned services to their clients. Currently, research has shown that the users of these services are more prevalent in urban and rural areas. Most customers aren't even aware that these services are available. The main causes for this are...

1. As they must rely on someone, customers may lose their freedom of privacy in conducting their money transactions.
2. Aversion to technological difficulties and transactional failures.
3. Financial loss and theft.
4. A lack of knowledge of technology.
5. Lack of willingness to adapt because they are at ease with old-age finance.

Professionals who work for themselves are occupied with their usual work schedules and business transactions on typical working days. They will have very little time to continue traveling to the banks, conduct their usual business, and fulfill their financial obligations once they are fully backed up at their place of business. The self-employed professionals have generally appreciated when banks have implemented efforts for paperless transactions. The majority of them have even urged both their clients and their coworkers to use the same. In other words, this has also paved the way for cashless transactions, freeing people from having to carry around real cash and expose them to unforeseen risks. Banks can also reduce their printing expenses. The majority of the independent professionals in the study region (Puttur) have set up POS (Point of Sale) devices and downloaded mobile banking apps from their various banks. By enticing customers to make additional purchases, this will also help their company.

Literature Review:

S.NO	Authors	Context (Title)	Outcome/Recommendations
1.	Herath et al., (2022)	Green banking initiatives' effects on client satisfaction	The study's goal is to look into how various aspects of green banking initiatives affect customer satisfaction. Data was gathered using the primary information source. The data in the study were analyzed using both multiple regression modeling and descriptive statistics. The study's conclusions indicate that older customers who are less tech literate are less satisfied with green banking features.
2.	Madhumathi & Nagadeepa (2020)	Acceptance of E-Banking: A Study of the Variations in Rural Customers' Demographics Regarding Tumkur Taluk	The research was carried out to look at the demographic preferences of customers for e-banking services. Primary statistics were used to gather the information's source. According to the research, customers vary noticeably depending on their demographic profile.
3.	Deka (2012)	An empirical study of SBI working in Jorhat reveals how customers use green banking practices.	The study looks at how SBI and its clients are adopting green banking practices using secondary sources of data. According to the study, using ATMs is preferable to using

			other green banking features. The study suggests that the bank launch a number of campaigns to raise client knowledge of green banking.
4.	Gon & Mititelu (2016)	CSR Activities in Top Indian Banks	The research investigates the spread and integration of CSR policies into corporate banking using secondary sources of data. The research demonstrated that new global guidelines and the core value of CSR have little impact on corporate banking at the national level.
5.	Tejaswini (2019)	Customer perceptions of green funding	The study using both primary and secondary sources of information, the study will look at the various green banking products and initiatives implemented by both public and private sector banks to raise consumer awareness. According to the study's findings, most literate customers have a favorable opinion of green banking goods.
6.	Sahi (2017)	An Empirical Investigation into Consumer Viewpoints on Green Banking: The Changing Banking Environment.	The study seeks to provide information on customers' knowledge of green banking initiatives, frequency of use of green services, and perceptions of the benefits of doing so. According to the study, most customers support green banking initiatives regardless of their level of education.
7.	Paluri & Mehra (2018)	The effect of corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives at banks on the attitudes and happiness of Indian consumers	The research was done to better understand how consumers felt about the CSR efforts of local banks. The statistics were gathered using primary sources of data. The research discovered that customer attitudes and

			satisfaction have an impact on bank CSR initiatives. Additionally, it was advised that banks should inform their customers about their CSR efforts.
8.	Sreesha (2014)	An examination of green banking efforts by India's private and public sector banks	The study is being carried out to investigate different models or channels for turning bank branches green. It also concentrated on Green Banking initiatives implemented by private and public sector banks in India to promote environmental sustainability. According to the study, public sector banks have done more green banking initiatives than private sector banks.
9.	Tara & Kumar (2015)	Indian green banking: opportunities and problems	The research looks at how green banking products are used by customers of various ages. ANOVA and post hoc test methods are used to analyze the study's goals. According to the research, there are notable differences between young and middle-aged consumers' usage of green banking products. People from the younger age groups are more interested in green banking projects than those from the middle age groups. So, the research suggested for conducting more awareness programs to middle age class customers.
10.	Vadrale & Katti (2016)	Green finance initiatives made by Indian state-owned and private sector banks	The study was performed to better understand the use of Green Banking Products in the banking sector and to investigate the green banking efforts of the top three public and private sector banks.

			According to the research, both private and public banks have successfully implemented green banking practices. It was also discovered that public sector banks are more successful than private sector banks in terms of green banking initiatives.
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Research Gap

Based on the investigate of earlier examines it is noticed that the examines were primarily focused on perception and satisfaction of customers toward green banking efforts on public and private sectors banks in India but no examines were individually carried out on the thinking of independent occupation towards green banking efforts on public sector banks at Puttur taluk in Dakshina Kannada Districts. The current study aims to better comprehend how independent contractors perceive green banking initiatives of public sector banks.

Research Objectives

The following objectives of this study are listed, and they are meant to be fulfilled:

1. To investigate the benefits of green funding.
2. To find out how well-educated independent contractors are about the green banking initiatives of their banks.
3. Analyzing the reactions to and satisfaction with green finance.
4. To show findings in accordance with the project evaluation.

Hypotheses

- 1) **H₁**: Awareness degree and intended use are unrelated concepts.
- 2) **H₀**: The use of green banking services and the degree of satisfaction of respondents are unrelated.

Methodology

This study relied on both primary and secondary sources. Primary data is collected through an oral interview as well as a questionnaire distributed to respondents. Secondary data is collected from publications such as banking journals, bank annual reports, books, newspapers, and related websites. The collected data is then tallied and submitted to non-parametric analysis. The study's sample size is restricted to 50 participants in the Puttur taluk of the Dakshina Kannada District, which is the designated study area. For this study, convenient selection was used. The respondents chosen are self-employed company owners. In particular, there are 12 hardware store owners in the neighborhood, 10 kirana store owners, 8 shoe dealers, 6 produce and fruit vendors, 4 bakeries, and 10 mobile and electronic shop owners are the target population.

Result and Discussion

Data is analyzed based on the responses of the interviewees. These responses are based on information collected through questionnaires given to respondents.

Table 1: Age distribution of respondents

Age	Number of responses	Percentage (%)
25 - 40	22	44
41 - 50	16	32
Above 50	12	24
	50	100

Table 2 Shows the gender of the respondents

Gender	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	44	88
Female	06	12
	50	100

Table 3: Business type of respondents

Nature of business	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Dealer	12	24
Distributor	14	28
Trader	24	48
	50	100

Table 4: Respondents of current Banker

Banker	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Corporation	16	32
SBI	08	61
Canara	20	40
Syndicate	04	08
Vijaya	02	04
	50	100

Table 5: Respondents banking experience

Banking knowledge (in years)	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Less than 3	16	32
3 – 5	20	40
Above 5	14	28
	50	100

Table 6: Respondents' knowledge of green finance

Awareness level	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly aware	30	60
Aware	20	40
	50	100

Table 7: The aim of green banking according to respondents

Purpose	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Convenience	20	40
Environmental concern	12	24
Time and cost saving	18	36

	50	100
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Table 8: Respondents' types of green banking activities

Type	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Mobile and internet banking	35	70
POS machine	15	30
	50	100

Table 9: Perception rating of green banking by respondents

Perception rating	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	10	20
Good	14	28
Average	18	36
Satisfactory	08	16
	50	100

Table 10: Respondents' degree of satisfaction with green banking

Satisfaction level	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	14	28
Satisfied	24	48
Not satisfied	12	24
	50	100

Chi square test

In this research, the chi square test is used to examine the relationship between two attributes. It is provided by

$$\text{Chi square} = \sum (O - E)^2 / E$$

In this formula, "O" stands for the measured frequencies, "E" for the anticipated frequency ranges, and "r" for the degree of freedom. (c - 1). In cases where the calculated chi square is lower than the tabulated chi square, the null hypothesis is accepted; in cases where it is greater, it is denied.

1.H: Awareness degree and intended use are unrelated concepts.

Awareness level	Purpose of using green banking			Total
	Convenience	Environmental concern	Time saving	
Highly aware	14	07	09	30
Aware	06	05	09	20
Total	20	12	18	50

Chi square has a table value of 5.991 at degrees of freedom (r - 1) and is calculated at 0.8963. (c - 1). The table value of the Chi square is therefore greater than the calculated value. There is acceptance of the null hypothesis.

2. H₀: The use of green banking services and the degree of satisfaction of respondents are unrelated.

Green banking services	Satisfaction level			Total
	Highly satisfied	Satisfied	Not satisfied	
Mobile and E-Banking	09	19	07	35
POS machine	05	05	05	15
Total	14	24	12	50

Chi square is 1.954 and has a table value of 5.991 when the degrees of freedom are $(2 - 1)(3 - 1) = 2$. Therefore, the Chi square's table value is higher than its computed value. This statement is true.

Findings

The study's results are as follows:

1. The majority of the replies come from men.
2. Those with 3 to 5 years of financial experience outnumber those without.
3. Very informed about green financial transactions are 60% of the respondents. 40% of the users use green banking for quick transactions.
4. Only 30% of respondents use POS machines for their transactions, while 70% use smartphones and internet banking.
5. Green finance is considered average by 36% of the participants in the poll.
6. According to 48% of respondents, green institutions' services are satisfactory.
7. There is no connection between the respondent's desire to pursue green finance and the extent of his or her familiarity with it. (Chi square test).
8. The respondents' satisfaction level and their use of green financial services are unrelated to one another. (Chi square).

Suggestions

The following suggestions are given by the respondents which are worth considering:

1. Educating rural women folk and senior residents on how to use green banking.
2. Periodic awareness campaigns must be launched to inform and persuade consumers to choose green banking.
3. From time to time, rebates and incentives should be offered for any purchases made using green banking. This will not only encourage them but also persuade other clients to follow suit.

Scope of the study

Customers are becoming more numerous every day and are quickly becoming conscious of green banking initiatives and technology-based products, so their concern for conserving future resources is very beneficial to them in one way or another. However, it is crucial to spread knowledge for all important clients, particularly those who live in rural, remote areas where technology is still out of their grasp but are suffering from the effects of climatic change. Power outages, signal & network issues, etc., are one of the main obstacles that must be overcome as soon as feasible in this area. This is the main reason that people in rural areas still feel at ease using traditional banking systems and are very hesitant to embrace changes in modern banking trends. Banks still need to make a lot of efforts to teach these customers and, if possible, assist them in engaging in technology-based transactions. It is feasible to conduct deeper research on the use of green banking services by interviewing members of the salaried class or the general public. This can be accomplished by using larger samples and a broader study area.

Constraints of the research

The following limitations of this research have been noted, and they are as follows:

1. Only fifty respondents were gathered for this research because there weren't many entrepreneurs involved.
2. Due to time restrictions, a smaller geographic area is selected.
3. Data is collected from the self-employed during their incredibly busy schedules and from a few of them after work hours because everything needs to line up precisely.
4. Because public sector banks are more prevalent in the study area, private sector banks are not included in this study.
5. Since self-employed business owners were reluctant to discuss their money, inquiries about the turnover of their enterprise were not answered.

Conclusion

Resources are being conserved and future generations of people are being protected through green finance initiatives. This will help customers complete their transactions swiftly, efficiently, and easily while also helping bankers increase their clientele and volume of business. Sustainable banking will be the way Indian banking develops in the future because younger groups prefer it. Instead of visiting a bank location, they favor doing their banking online.

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